

FROM THE HISTORY OF MANAGEMENT IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The main goal of development of the oil and gas industry in uzbekistan – fuel resources and increasing the effectiveness of the use of these resources by all sectors of the economy radically sustainable focuses on the population. The development of the oil and gas industry, above all, were put on the right path in the field of governance is directly associated with. In this thesis, covering management issues in the oil and gas industry in uzbekistan.

Keywords: "Fuel direktoriyasi", "Turktop", "Uzmeliomashlizing" trust, "the Sredazneft", "Fergananeft", "Andijonneft", "Jarqo'rg'onneft".

125 years of oil production in uzbekistan, while gas production more than half a century of historical experience. As it is known, in October 1917, a year after the soviet system, the country as a government is to become fully of turkistan carried out steadily. Carried out in the year of 1924 national-territorial national of the republic due to the limit of the central asian region, including the organization of the Uzbek ssr. For this reason the management system of the oil industry in the region also change depending on the state of the system go.

After the installation of soviet domination in the land, the country steadily in the soviet system the supreme economic council of the republic of fully existing oil fields to be addressed by the office of registrar of mining was introduced[1]. Later under the council "fuel direktoriyasi", 1922 in place in January this year, the director of "Ugleneft" trust was established. And this confidence came in October 1923 "Turktop" trust you to come to the year 1925 "Uzmeliomashlizing" trust is to become[2]. In 1930 "Uzmeliomashlizing" the end of trust, and in its place

"Sredazneft" trust in the organization found. In 1936, while on the basis of this trust and use them in order to search of oil deposits in the fergana valley "Kalininneft" trust, Surkhandarya, bukhara and kashkadarya region, as well as the Vakhsh valley (Tajik SSR) in search of work get to go to the territory of "Termizneft of trust" was established[3]. In 1948 both be combined on the basis of trust "Sredazneft" association was founded.

In 1964, after the organization of the ministry of oil and gas industry in the former soviet union, in particular to be associated with the development of gas industry in the ministry of gas industry was established. These changes on the basis of the soviet ministerial o'zssr January 7, 1966, № 8 dated according to the temporary is located in the city of Andijan, uzbekistan implied, the oil industry in the management of the network "Uzmeliomashlizing" extraction and production of oil in the republic of the union association was established[4]. In 1967, the soviet Ministerial O'zSSR № 243, dated, according to andijan and tashkent moved to the city from the city of associations[5]. October 1 in the year of 1975, while associations "Uzmeliomashlizing" production association was re-established. "Uzmeliomashlizing" associations operating in the structure of the network "Fergananeft", "Andijonneft", "Jarqo'rg'onneft" the organizations of the department of oil deposits and wells drilled – "Buxoroburneft", "Qo'qonburneft", "Andijonburneft", "Surxonburneft" directory is included. Also, supervisory gas industry in 1975 "Uzbekgazprom" production association was founded. "Uzbekgazprom" structure "while Transgaz" department "Gazligazdobicha", "Muborakgazdobicha", mubarek gas processing plant and other businesses were established. To achieve its independence under a combination of up to 12 thousand kilometers uzbekistan the main gas pipelines, compressor station 25 units, underground warehouses, as well as two research institutes, the design bureau of the plant from the work of the apparatus of gas[6]. In this regard it is worth mentioning,

these structures is primarily based on the interests of the center is to organize and direct the work activities of the union served to the center.

“Uzmeliomashlizing” association and “Uzbekgazprom” production association in the first years of independence of the state, functioning until 1992, development of certain activities in the area, construction work, mining work carried out in preparation for use. However, the resources and riches, including oil and gas without the bulk of which is rich territory due to activity of the enterprise sector in Uzbekistan after the subscriber oil industry of the republic as cover the necessary requirements for using quotes products new product grow.

In 1992, the government of the republic of activity of enterprises of the oil and gas industry, as defined by the strategic importance of the basic functions of the consistent implementation of measures on the implementation of the government of the republic started with clearly defined. First of all, in bulk in order to coordinate the activities of the business enterprise sector implemented radical changes in the management area. The president of the republic of Uzbekistan 3, 1992-may № № 393 decree dated[7] according to “O'zbekneftegaz” kontserni the state of the oil and gas industry of Uzbekistan was established.

Uzbekistan's oil and gas fields development and effective management of complex structure receives further improvement of the structural division, increase independence and initiative, consumers of oil, oil products and gas market relations in order to ensure necessary and reliable with the requirements of the industry come to the end of the year without considering organizational and administrative changes in the system are implemented. In particular, according to the decree of the president of the republic of Uzbekistan on 23 December 1992, the oil and gas industry of Uzbekistan oil and gas industry was transformed into the national kontserni korporasiyasi[8]. Activity on the basis of resolutions of the cabinet of ministers of the republic of Uzbekistan, showing “coming O'zbekgazsanoat” and

"Uzmeliomashlizing" production association was the end. The configuration of the corporation of the oil and gas industry the state of the control and coordination of the activities of the enterprise network-joint, the state production and scientific production associations included. The founders of these measures with the participation of shareholders in the role of the state and marks the first stage of description of the term you gave.

Conclusion words, and consistently carried out in the country in the years of independence ettirilayotir the radical changes continue today as a result of the formation of market relations in the sphere of oil and gas industry, the area and the requirements of the market economy on the basis of the enterprises of sphere in terms of the management of the organization clearly defined targeted measures are effectively implemented.

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